

THE IMPACT OF VERTEBRAL COLUMN DISEASES ON PATIENTS' DAILY ACTIVITIES

Prandzhev V.,

MD, PhD student in Faculty of Public Health „Prof. Tzekomir Vodenicharov, MD, DSc”

Petkova D.

Medical University-Sofia, Sofia, Bulgaria

ABSTRACT

Vertebral column diseases can have an impact on the patients' quality of life, as they can lead to serious disabling conditions. The goal of this research is to study and analyse the presence of difficulties that patients with vertebral column diseases may encounter in carrying out their day-to-day activities. The challenges that those patients may face in completing their housework in an adequate and timely manner have been studied, analysed and assessed herein. The challenges that they may face in their workplace or school when it comes to fulfilling their responsibilities well, on time and in their entirety were also studied.

Keywords: diseases, vertebral column, everyday activities.

Diseases of the spinal vertebrae, the intervertebral disks, the joints that connect them and the muscles located in the area of the back, which affect the peripheral nerve roots, cause spontaneous pain, tightness, limited range of motion and deformities. The pain can be local, constant, dull or burning and it can be accompanied by disturbances of the normal posture (1,2). Often there is sharp, acute pain that spreads from the spine to the affected arm or leg, which intensifies at sneezing or coughing. In some cases muscle weakness and atrophied muscles can be observed. All of this worsens those patients' quality of life and can lead to them facing challenges in carrying out their day-to-day activities. (3, 4)

The goal of this research is to study and analyse the presence of difficulties that patients with vertebral column diseases may encounter in carrying out their day-to-day activities.

In order to achieve the goal of the study, the following tasks were set:

1. Researching the difficulties the respondents have face in their completing of household duties.
2. Studying the difficulties the patients participating in the research may face in finishing all their housework in an adequate and timely manner.
3. Researching the difficulties the respondents have face in completing the routine activities at school or at the workplace.
4. Studying the difficulties the patients participating in the research have face in finishing all their work at school or at their workplace in an adequate and timely manner.

Methods. A questionnaire survey was conducted among patients with vertebral column diseases, who were treated in the Neurosurgery clinic at The Military Medical Academy (MMA) in Sofia during the 01.02.2023 - 30.04.2023 period. The principles of voluntary participation and anonymity were upheld. There were 150 patients with vertebral column diseases who participated. The WHO Disability Assessment Schedule 2.0 (WHODAS 2.0) questionnaire was used for the purposes of the research. It was developed by the organisation's experts and is used to study challenges to functioning in six selected domains for a period of 30 days before date of the study (5). The current article

presents the results of the fifth domain from the WHODAS 2.0 questionnaire, which was used to assess the health and disability status of patients hospitalised in the Neurosurgery clinic. The fifth domain, which is studied here, includes questions regarding challenges with completing everyday activities for patients with vertebral column diseases. Those are activities that people do on a daily basis and which encompass housework chores, work activities and school activities. The degree of difficulty for completing the activities in the areas studied is assessed on a polytomous (multi-level) scale - "I don't experience any difficulties", "mild difficulties", "moderate difficulties", "severe difficulties" and "extreme difficulties/cannot do".

Results.

In the course of the study, 150 patients treated at the Neurosurgery clinic at MMA-Sofia responded to the questionnaire. Of them, 36% were women and 64% were men.

The average age of the respondents is 51,23 (+/- 2,10). More than half of the respondents - 52,7% reside in the capital, 25,3% in towns, 14% in province center towns, and 8% are village residents. 54,7% of the respondents have a higher education diploma (Bachelor's degree - 24%, and Master's Degree - 30,7%), 28% have a Vocational Bachelor's degree, while 7,3% have a doctorate. The respondents with secondary education are 8,7%. Those who have only completed primary education are 1,3%. The nature of this educational level is such that we can expect adequate understanding of the questions asked and highly accurate answers.

The first question from the research domain is aimed at establishing the degree to which the respondents have experienced health-related challenges in completing their household chores during the previous 30 days. This question requires that the respondents assess the degree of difficulty they have experienced in maintaining their household or caring for their family members, or for other relatives and close friends. All household and family needs are included in this question, incl. physical needs, emotional needs, financial needs and psychological needs. Household duties also include the following:

- finance management
- automobile and home repairs

- maintaining the area surrounding the home
- picking children up from school
- helping the children with their homework
- disciplining the children.

The analysed results from the questionnaire show that 44% of the participating patients experience

"severe difficulties" in fulfilling their household duties, followed by 34,7% who report that experiencing "extreme difficulties/cannot do". One fifth (21,3%) of the respondents report that their difficulties are "moderate". (Figure 1.)

Figure 1. Distribution frequency of the respondents according to the presence of difficulties in fulfilling their household duties

The next question from the this domain is aimed at analysing to what degree, during the previous 30 days, the respondents have experienced health-related challenges in doing the most important household chores well. Impairments associated with vertebral

column diseases can lead to challenges in completing household chores well for the patients. This is clear from the results obtained in this survey - 67.3% have reported "extreme difficulties/cannot do", while for 32.7% those difficulties are "severe". (Figure 2.)

Figure 2. Distribution frequency of the respondents according to the presence of difficulties in fulfilling their household duties well

The two next questions from the this domain are aimed at analysing to what degree, during the previous 30 days, the respondents have experienced health-related challenges in:

➤ completing their housework in its entirety - the participants have given their assessment of how well they have done their domestic tasks and whether all the housework that should have been completed have been completed.

➤ finishing their housework in time - this question is related to the degree to which the expectations and needs of the respondents, with which one lives (or is close to), as to the tasks and responsibilities of the household, were fulfilled in a timely manner.

The results of these questions are presented on Figure 3 and Figure 4.

Figure 3. Distribution frequency of the respondents according to the presence of difficulties in completing their housework in its entirety

Figure 4. Distribution frequency of the respondents according to the presence of difficulties in completing their housework on time

68% of the participants respond that they experience "extreme difficulties/ cannot do" in completing all of their housework, and almost the same amount (66%) report to have "extreme difficulties/cannot do" in completing their housework in time. Almost a third of the respondents (32%) have had "severe difficulties" in completing all of their housework, and 34% have experience "severe difficulties" in completing their housework in time.

Impairments seen in patients with vertebral column diseases can also lead to disturbances and limitations in keeping up with work/school responsibilities. The four next questions from this domain were asked in relation to this. They are aimed at establishing to what degree, during the previous 30 days, the respondents have experienced health-related challenges in:

- completing the routine tasks at school/work;
- completing their task i school/work well;
- complete the work in its entirety;
- to complete their work in time.

The question on the completion of routine tasks is aimed at studying the respondents' assessment of the

difficulties they encounter in completing their routine activities at school or at work. This includes activities such as arriving for work/school on time, the skills to work/study under supervision, supervising others, planning and organisation, satisfying expectations at the workplace, and other activities.

For work/school tasks to be completed "well", it is expected that they are done in a manner that meets the expectations of the direct supervisor or the teacher, the respondent's personal standards, or the performance criteria for the respective position or the school in question.

The questionnaire-style survey found that the same relative share of respondents - 53.3%, have reported experiencing "severe difficulties" in fully completing their routine tasks at the workplace/school and in doing those tasks "well" (Figure 5 and Figure 6). 32% of the participants have experienced "moderate difficulties" in completing their tasks, while 4% report their difficulties are "extreme". For the remaining 10.7% those difficulties are "mild". (Figure 5)

Figure 5. Distribution frequency of the respondents according to the presence of difficulties in completing routine tasks at the workplace/school

25% of the respondents have experienced "extreme difficulties/cannot do" in doing their tasks well at work/school, and in 10.7% of the participants those difficulties were respectively "moderate" and "mild". (Figure 6.)

Figure 6. Distribution frequency of the respondents according to the presence of difficulties in completing their tasks well at work/school

The following questions relate to meeting the expectations for the amount of work productivity and meeting work deadlines. Analyzing the extent to which respondents have experienced difficulties in doing all the entirety of their work reveals that more than half - 53%, have reported "severe" difficulties, and 36% - "extreme difficulties/cannot do". (Figure 7.)

Figure 7. Distribution frequency of the respondents according to the presence of difficulties in completing their work in its entirety

In over half of the respondents (57.4%) answered "extreme difficulties/ cannot do" when asked whether they have experienced difficulties in completing their work on time, followed by 21.3% who reported "mild" and "moderate" difficulties. (Figure 8.)

Figure 8. Distribution frequency of the respondents according to the presence of difficulties in completing their work in time

We can draw the following conclusions from the survey and analysis of the challenges patients with vertebral column diseases face in completing everyday activities:

1. The majority of the respondents (78.7%) have "severe" or "extreme/cannot do" difficulties in fulfilling their household responsibilities due to the severity of their illness.
2. 68% of the respondents experience "extreme/cannot do" difficulties in getting all their housework done and almost the same percentage (66%) report that their difficulties are "extreme/cannot do" when asked if they can finish all their housework in time.
3. The relative portion of the respondents who have experienced "severe" difficulties in both completing all their routine tasks at work/school and doing their tasks well is the same at 53.3%.
4. Over half the patients who participated (53%) have experienced "severe" difficulties, and 36% report

having had "extreme/cannot do" difficulties in completing their work in its entirety, which has an effect on their emotional state and worsens their quality of life.

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